

TEACHING A LETTER OF COMPLAINT TO 7TH GRADE SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH COMMUNICATIVE VISUAL-SITUATIONAL APPROACH

Aziza Hazratova

MA student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Scientific advisor:

Raimova K.B.,

senior teacher of USWLU

Annotation: *This research was done to compare traditional approach and communicative visual-situational approach while teaching a letter of complaint to 7th grade students of Uzbekistan. Students and teachers of ESL from 26th school of Zhondor, Bukhara were selected as a population of the study. The major purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of a curricular sequence of oral language experiences upon the subsequent writing performance of a selected group of seventh graders. A secondary purpose of the study was to determine the effect of oral language practice upon children's written language usage and mechanics of English. Two separate groups were taught through two different approaches. The collection of data was analyzed with pre-test, post-test, mean, standard deviation and t-test. Data analyses revealed that tradition approach being utilized in teaching a letter of complaint in L2 cannot promote adequate knowledge to students. It is revealed from the study that if a foreign language writing skill is taught through communicative visual-situational approach the language can be acquired fast and effective. During the study students improved not only their writing skill (knowledge of writing complaint letter) but also their communicative competence, listening comprehension and critical thinking ability.*

Keywords: *a letter of complaint, traditional approach, communicative visual-situational approach, data analyses, listening comprehension, communicative competence, critical thinking ability.*

Introduction

English language is being dominant in all spheres of life such as: IT, business, education, international relationship and so forth. For this reason, demand for English language acquisition is also increasing over the globe. In Uzbekistan even five-year children start to learn English language in their kindergartens, in language learning centers and from their parents. The major aim of those children is to be master at foreign language and their majors. They generally understand that English language is required in almost all professions. Thus, new approaches, methods and techniques are being implemented in education (especially in language teaching in order improve the quality and decrease the period of teaching and learning a foreign language). In the teaching learning process of foreign or second language English, countless approaches and methods are used and still using to reach the academic and individual goals in English language LSRW skills acquisition. While looking at the difference between approach and methods, Approach refers to

“theories about the nature of language and language learning that serve as the source of practices and principles in language teaching” (Richards and Rodgers, 1986) and Method/Methodology refers to “the level at which theory is put into practice and at which choices are made about the particular skills to be taught, the content to be taught, and the order in which the content will be presented” (Richards and Rodgers, 1986). One of those modern approaches to foreign language teaching is communicative visual-situational approach.

Statement of the issue. In this work, I decided to provide the comparative analyses of traditional approach and communicative visual-situational approach in teaching writing and effects of communicative visual-situational approach in learning process. With this work I want to show how fast writing skill in English language can be learnt. Through this approach students can improve not only their writing ability but also their cognitive power, analyzing skill, listening talent, communication, pronunciation and community skills. I

also attempt to show beneficial impacts of new approach, communicative visual-situational approach, while teaching writing skill to English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. In this study I am going to compare traditional approach and communicative visual-situational approach in teaching writing a complaint letter in English language to 7th grade school students of Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

1. Review of literature.

Research studies in creative writing have apparently accumulated rapidly since 1963 when Shane (1963:61) reported finding little or no research specifically devoted to this topic. The question of what and how to teach pupils so that quantity and quality of writing were improved seemed to have motivated the bulk of research in creative writing. The evaluation of the writing product has also received some attention. The research is based on the literary texts taken from the works by Francis Setonji Yede, Geraldine

Marie Kinchen (An Oral-Aural-Visual Approach to Written Communicative Ability of Selected Third-Grade Students).

Research hypothesis.

There three hypothesis of this research:

1. Communicative visual-situational approach is more effective in teaching a letter of complaint in English language compared to traditional approach.
2. Students can learn faster writing complaining letter through communicative visual-situational approach than traditional approach.
3. Students improve not only writing a complaint letter skill but also other skills such as, listening, speaking, critical thinking and so forth.

2. Research study.

The aim of the research is to increase practical achievements in teaching writing a letter of complaint through using new communicative visual-situational approach.

To achieve the aim, the following tasks were set:

- To differentiate the convergences and divergences of traditional and communicative visual-situational approaches in teaching writing complaint letter to L2 students;
- To find out the beneficial aspects of communicative visual-situational approach;
- To find out the ways of improving students' organization and writing skills simultaneously with the aid of communicative visual-situational approach;
- To improve the other skills at the same time with writing complaint letter skill.

a) Research method.

This research is mixed type of research, since there one can see elements of both qualitative and quantitative methods.

- Descriptive and analytical methods have been used to analyze the benefits of using communicative visual-situational approach in

teaching writing a letter of complaint;

- Data analysis method while analyzing collected data.
- Participant observations method to monitor participation of selected student in both groups.
- Experimental method

b) Instruments for data analyses.

While analyzing collected data, I used the statistical tools of JASP statistics program. The following tools were utilized in my research: t-test, p evaluation, standard deviation, mean, pre-test, post-test.

5. Results and discussion.

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of real communicative visual situation to improve students writing skill. In the study students were divided in two (experimental and control) groups and showed a real situation to the experimental group and discussed with students, finally, asked to write a complaint letter according to the situation. However to the control group according to the traditional

way of teaching writing teacher explained the structure of writing complaint letter and asked to write a letter. In the following tables it will be

clear the differences between groups to the acquisition of writing a complaint letter.

Table 1
Distribution of Raw Scores: Complaint letter

Raw Scores	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
3	26	7	23	4
4	9	3	8	2
5	2	3	3	3
6	4	2	4	2
7	0	3	1	7
8	1	8	1	6
9	0	8	2	4
10	1	4	0	3
11	0	1	0	5
12	0	3	0	4
13	0	0	1	1
14	0	1	0	1
15	0	0	0	1
N =	43	43	43	43

A comparison of means of the pre-test and post-test complaint letters revealed that gains were made by both the experimental and control groups with a slight difference

favoring the experimental group. The means and standard deviations of the complaint letter raw scores were presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Means and Standard Deviations of
Raw Scores: Complaint letter

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
Mean	3.86	7.40	4.33	8.26
SD	1.49	2.90	2.12	3.07

There were no significant differences in the quality of compositions written by subjects receiving oral language practice and those who received traditional instruction in language. To meet the test of significance at the .05 level of confidence, F would have to be 3.98 or better (Garrett, 1966). The F-ratio of 1.08 did not meet this test of significance at the .05 level of confidence.

Conclusion

It is generally understood that English language is required in almost all professions. Thus, new approaches, methods and techniques are being implemented in education (especially in language teaching in order improve the quality and decrease the period of teaching and

learning a foreign language). One of those modern approaches to foreign language teaching is communicative visual-situational approach. In the research I put three main hypothesis to find solutions during the study. I selected several techniques and methods to collect data. I utilized the application of JASP statistics to show differences between two groups of students, those taught writing through communicative visual-situational approach and the others were taught writing in traditional way. It can be seen from provided results above, teaching writing to 7th grade school students through communicative visual-situational approach effected more beneficial compared to traditional methods, like: grammar translation, direct method.

According to the analyses, given above, students who were taught writing skill via CVSA (communicative visual-situational approach) could learn writing in a foreign language (English) faster than those, who were taught traditional

way. Students other skills, such as critical thinking, cognitive skill, communicative competence, listening comprehension and so forth are improved at the same time with writing skill in the process of teaching.

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